

A SOCIOLOGICAL ASSESSMENT OF THE AWARENESS LEVEL OF CIVIC RESPONSIBILITIES AMONG UNIVERSITY STUDENTS: A CASE STUDY OF BALUCHISTAN

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Abstract

To attain common objective and make progress, a society needs certain guiding principles. To a large extent, well established and recognized customary values can guarantee this aim of societal progressiveness, which can never let anyone divert or act contrary to the collective goals of society. Certain values have held together every society. These values and acts help to keep society running smooth, ensure security for future generations and help to keep people happy. Civic sense is unspoken norms of a society, the role of citizen in a society with specific values can also be considered as civic sense, Nation and societies need certain guiding principle to attain common objective and make progress. The research study intended to explore the status of the noncompliance to civic values and further revealed the root causes and contributing factors for noncompliance to the civic values. Remedial measures were suggested based on the findings of the study. Certain values have held together in every society. These values and acts help to keep society running smooth, ensure security for future generations and help to keep people happy. The research methodology of this study is designed by considering the importance of viewpoints on multiple dimensions of the study, hence mixed method approach was applied by using both quantitative and qualitative for data collection. Quantitative method was used for conducting perception survey for gathering quantifiable information from the primary target group (students at universities in Quetta) of the population under study. From the qualitative methods perspective Key Informant Interviews (KIIs) conducted by selecting respondents from the university of Balochistan (University of Balochistan SBK, University of Turbat) who have potential and position to influence policy reforms. This thesis is explored the level of civic values and measured the student's level of understanding civic values and their role for contributing to community development.

Keywords: Civic Management Higher Education, Social Responsibilities, Civic Values, Civic Education, Community Development.

INTRODUCTION

Civic is known as social ethics and a social norm. civic provides a sense of responsibility to an individual to actively participate in community and society improvement and developmental affairs to ensure being an active and responsible citizen. Civic responsibility is about keeping the order of society smooth. Making society functional according to societal norms, values and most importantly following the law. The attainment of common goal and make society develop, some sort of guiding principle is needed to each society for large level. Well recognized and established customary values can be source of maintenance and provide societal progressiveness. Because the customary values are strong enough which cannot let individuals to distract and act contrary toward society's common goals. Each society has some specific values, by these values and acts people experience better life and enjoys the smooth-running o social life. These values certify safeguard o individuals or present but become source to ensure future generations security and become source keep people cheerful and happy (Bangwar, 2020).

The idea of a law-based society can be moved forward by empowering people to lock in decision making and have an intrigued in open arrangement talks about inside the society (Caputo, 2005). This puts forward the reality that civic engagement is instrumental to dynamic equitable society) since the reason for civic engagement in a popular government is to pursue equitable beliefs of equity and uniformity in a multicultural society. Civic engagement is generally related to community benefit, collective activity, dynamic citizenship, political involvement, and citizen interest in civic issues. Depending on its changed definitions, it includes both individual/informal exercises and collective/formal activities. Other than that, it incorporates the association in community exercises as well as the association in political exercises (Adler., and Goggin., 2005).

Civic responsibility refers to those responsibilities which are concern with citizenship (Delanty. G., 2007). Citizen having some sort of responsibilities whole living in community, society and in a country the citizen is obligated to assure some duties as well as of responsibilities to be own (Porter. M. E., and Kramer. M. R., 2006). To show gratitude's toward society or community well-being represent someone generosity toward society or community (Hart. R. A., 2013). It can be one's participation in political affairs like, voting, participate in open meeting promote the political campaign of the favorite party that going to give good results compared to other parties.

Background of the study

To get it to how civic engagement is worked out within the world, it is vital to consider its indicators. These pointers can be community issue fathoming, dynamic participation in a bunch or association, normal voting, convincing others, reaching authorities, dissenting, mail or written petitions, boycotting, showing signs, buttons, and stickers, campaign contributions (Adler and Goggin, 2005), daily paper readership, group participation, permitting others to talk (Dee, 2004), performing open benefit, taking an interest within the political prepare, working with deliberate groups (Downs, 2012), and so on. Advance recognize among four shapes of civic engagement: grassroots organizing (e.g., utilizing dissents and showings, gracious disobedience, presentations in open procedures, and arrangement of coalitions), citizen interest (e.g., voting in elections and talking at open hearings), intergroup exchange (Sullivan. P., 2014).

Citizenship its obligations and rights are considered as primary concepts problems and issues in modern time and the degree to which individuals are aware of them is one of the main determinant figures in actualizing the social approaches and tackling sociocultural issues (Sahabi. J., (2015). Nowadays, tackling numerous issues the society is facing needs techniques and awareness of the individual's behavior in society because awareness empowers them to request their rights. Other than, when individuals become aware of their rights, they can get commonplace of their obligation toward the community and other individuals. (Giannotti. F., 2012). Universally, youth have a basic part in social alter as dynamic citizens. In return, civic engagement helps to create particularly a youthful person's sense of having a place and commitment, sense of self-esteem, self-identity, and independence (Shaw et al., 2012)

Civic responsibility

Civic responsibility although not having any clear and definite meaning but many scholars and research hers have given their views accordingly (Kemmer's. R., 2017). Civic responsibility of citizens. These responsibilities connected with democratic societies and government (Gottlieb. K. and Robinson, 2006). Participation of people in social life (Turino. T., 2008). Briefly the civic responsibilities can fall working with voluntary association participation in church or mosque community-based association to make thy self as a volunteer (Deakin, N. 2001), action and activities fall under civic responsibility can be displayed likewise firstly to be preferred of the different cause of community wellbeing such

as civil, political, environmental. Political issues that making the quality of life low (Radcliff. B., 2013). Civically aware citizens show ore morality and activeness in community well-being (Klein. A. M. and Grandin. P. J., 2014).

LITERATURE REVIEW

The true aim of education is to inculcate positive changes among people for the growth of society. Individual in the society is involved with social activities. The true civic sense of people decides the quality to make decision which is good for their family and society. According to Oxford University dictionary “Civic sense refers to the ability of oneself abiding social rules, respecting fellow beings and maintaining public decorum in the public gathering “civic is in general term is an attitude that reflects equity and liberty in the society. Therefore, civic values have become backbone of any society in the world. The sense of true duty and responsibility is always link to civic values. It will strengthen the relationship among individual and society. Thus, civic sense is the true promoter of a successful life and enhances the social skills of individual within a society (Dr. P.P. Shajimon 2018).

Civic is a social norm and social ethics. It gives an individual a sense of responsibility to become an active citizen in the society. It is about keeping the functional of the society and following the laws and social norms (Bhatia 2015). In 1787, Thomas Jefferson said in a letter to James Madison, “above all things I hope the education of the common people will be attended to, convinced that on their good sense we may rely with the most security for the preservation of a due degree of liberty” (Jefferson and Burton, 1958). Civic sense has always been part of curricula of many countries, aim to inculcate sense of civilization and bring social responsibility. Civic sense meaningfully transforms the values and norms of the society and determines the values of individual in the social context. Apart from this, Socialization is always linked with civic sense, sense socialization is the most fundamental determinants of people’s behavior, from family to peer group (RATHORE 2016). Thus, civic is all about care for fellow humans. It generally means being civilized and helpful showing respect to elders, women, and neighbor.

Youth development has great relationship with civic engagement. Civic engagement is a process contributes to individual well-being and positive development and particularly society. Many past studies have shown that civic sense politely influences the mentality of adolescence and adulthood. Critical societies provide youth with civic sense to bring development in their community (Rossi 2016). Developing countries giving great importance to democracy rather than other government system. But emerging social and

economic inequalities are threatening the stability of democratic government. Several studies of developing countries highlighted the importance of encouraging and strengthening citizenship education among the people of nation to make democracy more sustainable (Cox, 2005). Civic learning and attitude are recognized a nourishing tool for civic learning. Civic learning mentions to promote justice, equality, tolerance and developing harmony and responsibility to a public good (Keen, 2009). Another study conducted that civic sense and values create clean up environment and encourage responsible behavior towards prosperous life activities (Lott, 2011). Role of media is considered essential predictor of modifying civic values. Media cultivates the behavior of citizens in civic engagement to cope with several issues in society (Gerbner, 1972). Another study demonstrated that the social and cultural values are almost injected by media to encourage civic responsibility among citizens reshaped the opinions about civic life (Swigger, 2013). Another study argued that there is no link between social media and civic learning. It has found internet usage disconnect the people from their social gathering such as family, friends and spoil their role in civic engagement with social circle (Kraut, 1998)

According to the American scholars and political experts, the survival of the social and democratic institutions depends on all citizen who dare to put efforts for the welfare of the community members. The existing communities ensure all high-quality civic values and education. The past researchers suggest that number of citizens around the globe continue to be very ignorant who are failed to address their community needs and demands. They surely deprived of real knowledge and social sense of responsibility. They are failed to gain more knowledge about politics, culture, and social justice. Currently, a service-learning tool and process has explained that there is a dire need of increasing students learning and limited knowledge about democratic politics and civic values and inculcate them a sense of social responsibility. The service-learning tool is experimental education system that provide opportunities for learning new academic skills that would reflect the normative dimensions of civic life (Susan Hunter, 2013). It is worldwide believed that formal learning is a process that can positively influence the social attitudes and behaviors of people and motivate them to take part in civic responsibilities. At this stage the social sciences and humanities are found to be very sufficient as more likely associated with social values and responsibilities (Paterson, 2009).

The previous studies suggested that formal and moral education leads people towards gaining social and civic values. Education has a positive effect on level of

community participation and level of socially liberal views. It is suggested that, rising in educational level would like create a more social and liberal societies. Some important feature of education reflects socially accepted values and guide people to conform on them. There is always a link to parental education that influences civic values within a community.

METHODOLOGY

The introduction research chapter starts with the methods and techniques of Research. It discusses the theoretical underpinning and ideas behind this Research, and it will explain a brief explanation of this overall research and the paradigm used. This chapter discusses the rationale behind this selection of this research design. Besides this, it will explain the research questions and methods to answer those research questions. It will also cover data collection Methods, sampling, and particular method of data analysis. The mixed-method approach was used in the present research to find out the student's awareness level about civic responsibility and to investigate their perception regarding civic responsibility that how students are concern about community well-being by engaging themselves in community improvement activities, the study also looked that how community involvement brings changes in the students' practical lives. in the chapter of methodology, the research design, sampling, research procedures, research instrument, mixed-method data processing is used and discussed in the details.

RESEARCH DESIGN

To solve, the problem bottomless and the purpose of getting valid and reliable data on the topic this study was systematically conducted on the subject being studied. The research design of the present study was mix method (quantitative and qualitative method). The mixed method approach was used as the research design of the present research. The justification for the mixed method is that neither qualitative nor quantitative procedures are adequate by themselves to examine the detail and trends of the phenomena and situations, such as a multifaceted issue, determination in the distributed in knowledge gaining environment. Usage of a combination of qualitative and quantitative procedure complement each other and permit for more comprehensive analysis. In quantitative inquire, an agent depends on numerical information. Consecutively the qualitative method of research is a research procedure to understand wherever the investigator develops a complex complete nature of a detailed report analyzes words and views of informants researching a natural environment. According to Tashakkori and Teddlie (2009). Around Four deferent types of mixed research designs: 1) embedded 2 triangulations,3) exploratory and 4) explanatory. This research most appropriately applied the explanatory model.

TOOLS OF DATA COLLECTION

Questionnaires and interviews guide schedule was developed to collect data. The questionnaires comprised of close-ended questions and the interview guide comprised of open-ended questions. The in-depth interviews were used to know the perception of university students about civic values and engagement. The research being Mix method in nature would use non-participants' observation for data collection. The observation checklist was prepared to monitor students' personal views about civic engagement.

Universe of the present study (Research Site)

The research site chosen based on purpose of the research topic. In the study, the approach is used to select the study area where the researcher has conducted the research. The researcher willingly decides the site of the research where he or she are prevalent to study the social phenomena and social process (Silverman, 2001). In the present study the researcher will select the site, according to the nature and factors of the research.

The universe of the present study was the universities of Balochistan which include the University of Balochistan, Balochistan university information technology engineering and management sciences, university of Turbat and Sardar bahadur khan Women University were selected for purpose of data collection.

Strategy for entering research sites:

Conducting field research is more capable, that provide an interpretative approach to the researcher to conduct the research in a flexible and organized way. In the field it is necessary for the researcher to know and avail the opportunities for the purpose to be adjusted and quickly to be engaged with the social phenomena. This approach will open the doors for the researcher to learn and discover innovative ideas and the necessary tools for the researcher (Neuman, 2000). The researcher is supposed to organize some important plan and strategy before entering to the study area. It is very much important that the researcher is supposed to make sure negotiation and rapport building as well as gate keeping particularly experiencing the field in a meaningful way

DATA ANALYSIS

The fourth chapter deals with analyzing data which were gathered from different respondents through interviews and questionnaires. Total participants were 120 selected Underpinning the major concepts of the study the interviews were categorized into in-depth interviews and focus group discussion FDGS and for quantitative data analysis SPSS was used to measure the frequency and percentage. The interviews were conducted with the due

permission of universities of Balochistan. This chapter also discusses the observation of the researcher himself and his experiences.

Table 1

	Being a student university matters are your high priority	I am giving full time to my education	Reaching in first timing in your class is your indispensable priority	it is good to have personal strong connection to a specific community
strongly agree	34.2	27.5	30.8	35.0
Agree	40.0	38.3	34.2	35.0
Neutral	20.8	25.8	20.8	18.3
Disagree	.8	2.5	7.5	5.0
strongly disagree	4.2	5.8	6.7	6.7
	100.0	100.0	100.0	100.0

Figure 1

Table: 1.

The table and the above graphs revealed that, 74.2% student strongly agreed with the statement that university is their priority, and they give more time to their university as a responsible student. 5% disagreed by the given statement that portrayed by not listing university and their study on high priority and 20.8% remained neutral by their statement they were not sure whether they high priority to their university or not. In the second variable in the tables 64.10% strongly agreed being punctual and to give priority reaching at first time in their class. 6.7% disagreed and 20.8% remained neutral. In the third variable from the table showed that 70% of the respondent agreed to have personal connection to a specific community among them 11.7% disagreed and 18.3% of the respondent were not sure neither they agreed not disagree and remained neutral. In the fourth variable from the graphs and table 65.8% of the respondent strongly agreed giving full time to their education. 5% disagreed and 25.8% remained neutral.

Table 2

	social political and national or local issues positively influence the community	participating in social or political activities is a positive stance for the development of the community	always to obey laws	to keep an eye on government activities
strongly agree	35.8	36.7	54.2	43.3
Agree	26.7	35.0	27.5	31.7
Neutral	20.0	19.2	13.3	14.2
Disagree	11.7	4.2	2.5	4.2
strongly disagree	5.8	5.0	2.5	6.7
		100.0	100.0	100.0

Figure 2

Table: 2. The result from table two and mentioned graphs revealed that, 61.15% of the citizens believed that social national and local issues positively influence the community. And they were keen to observing social and national issues positively influence the community. 16.15% of the respondent disagreed with the statement and 20.0% of the respondent neither agreed not disagreed who remained neutral. In the second variable mentioned in the table, 71.6% believed that taking part in social and political issue is positive stance for the development of the community. They showed interest in taking part in certain activities. 9.2% of the respondent disagreed with the statement and 19.2% remained neutral. In third variable from the table and graphs 81.7 % of the citizen believed that it is good to obeys laws of the government. 4.10% disagreed with the statement and 13.3% remained neutral.

Table 3

	it is the basic responsibility of every citizen to actively vote an election	authorities treat everybody equally regardless of their position within the community	women and men equally participate in the community	all members of the community take social responsibility to solve community common
strongly agree	55.8	25.8	38.3	36.7
Agree	21.7	35.0	27.5	30.8
Neutral	11.7	15.8	15.8	15.8
Disagree	5.0	9.2	7.5	7.5
strongly disagree	5.8	14.2	10.8	9.2
	100.0	100.0	100.0	100.0

Figure 3

Table: 3. The Above result from the table and charts revealed that, 77.5% of the respondent believed that it is the responsibility of citizens to vote in every election. 10.8% of the participants did not agree with statement provided to them and 11.7 of the respondents neither agree to vote in election not disagreed they remained neutral. In the second statement it was revealed that, 60.8% of the respondent believed all citizen should be treated equally. 24.4% of the participants disagreed with the statement and 15.8% of the respondents remained neutral. From the third statement in the table 65.8% participants believed in equal participation of both men and women in the community. 17.5% of the respondent disagreed with the statement and 15.8% of the participants neither agreed with the statement not disagreed they remained neutral. Form the fourth variables it was revealed that 67.7% believed that taking social responsibility is a key to solving community problems. 16.7% of the respondent disagreed with the statement and 15.8% participants neither agreed nor disagreed they remained neutral.

Table 4

	all members of the community take social responsibility to solve community common	all citizens should struggle for the clean environment	all citizens have equal chance of living within the community	all members of the community must be given more opportunities to
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				take part in decision making
strongly agree	36.7	60.8	55.8	50.8
Agree	30.8	24.2	24.2	33.3
Neutral	15.8	5.0	10.0	10.0
Disagree	7.5	3.3	7.5	3.3
strongly disagree	9.2	6.7	2.5	2.5
	100.0	100.0	100.0	100.0

Figure 4

Table: 4. The result from table 4 and graphs revealed that, 67.5% of the respondents believed in taking social responsibility.16.7 of the participants did not believe in taking social responsibility and 15.8% of the respondent neither agreed nor disagreed they remained neutral. From the variable in the table and graphs 85% of the participants believed that all citizens should struggle for the clean environment. 11% of the respondent disagreed with the statement and 5% of the respondent neither agreed nor disagreed they remained

neutral. In the third variable 80% of the respondents believed that all members of the community should have an equal chance of living in the society. 10% of the respondent disagreed with the statement and 10% of the participants remained neutral. In the fourth variables 84.1% of the respondent emphasized on decision making for the development of the community. 5.8% of the participants disagreed and 10% remained natural

Table 5

	to be an active citizen, obeying the law is very important	every member must respect national anthem and flag	promoting community development is the basic duty of every citizen	the outcome is disadvantageous when someone contributes his/herself to the community indeed the cause is difficult and challenging
strongly agree	60.0	55.8	40.0	31.7
Agree	25.8	22.5	35.8	36.7
Neutral	10.0	12.5	15.0	24.2
Disagree	2.5	3.3	4.2	4.2
strongly disagree	1.7	5.8	5.0	3.3
	100.0	100.0	100.0	100.0

Figure 5

Table: 5.

The result from table 5 and graphs revealed that, 72.5% of the respondent believed that every member of the society should be aware of the community needs and demands. 10% of the respondents disagreed with the statement and 17.5 neither agreed nor disagreed. From the second variable it was revealed that, 73.3% of the participants believed in knowing the basic needs of the community. From the third variable 85.8% of the respondents believed to obey the government laws. 4.2% disagreed with statement and 10% of the respondent neither agreed nor disagreed they remained neutral. 78.3% credited respecting national anthem.

Table 6

	being member of the community, it is necessary to be aware of the needs and demands of the community	being familiar to know what steps are required to meet the indispensable needs of the community	improving community is something that members inclined towards and let others do	being an active citizen, I will engage my friends and neighbors for the wellbeing of the community	Every member is responsible for helping community members
strongly agree	34.2	40.8	25.0	34.2	34.2
Agree	38.3	32.5	41.7	35.8	35.8
Neutral	17.5	18.3	23.3	17.5	17.5
Disagree	6.7	5.0	6.7	9.2	9.2
strongly disagree	3.3	3.3	3.3	3.3	3.3
	100.0	100.0	100.0	100.0	100.0

Figure 6

Table: 6.

The result from table 6 and the charts revealed that, 72.5% respondent believed to know the needs and demands of the society. 10% of the participates disagreed with the statement. 17.5% of the respondents neither agreed nor disagreed they remained neutral. From the

second variable in the table, 73.3% respondents were aware about the steps and requirement to meet the necessary demands of the society. 8.3% of the participants were not aware about the needs and demands of the society and 18.3% of the respondents were neither aware nor unaware they remained neutral. In the third variable from the result, it was revealed that 66% of the respondents believed that every citizen should work for the development of the community and encourage others to do. 10% of the respondents did not agree with the statement. And 23.3% of the participants neither agreed nor disagreed they remained neutral. From the fourth variable in the table, it was revealed that, 71.7% of the respondent believed to work for the well-being of the community. 6% did not believe to work for the community and 21.7% neither agreed nor disagreed they remained neutral.

Table 7

	it is necessary to attempt to act on arrangements that addresses social political national or local problems of the community	active participation in social and political issues can be gateway for the community development	taking part in community development activities help in improving community	active citizen work for community development	being an active citizen, I will be responsible in arranging effective activities that can provide solution to community problems
Strongly Agree	45.0	45.0	34.2	28.3	36.7
Agree	29.2	29.2	36.7	45.0	32.5
Neutral	17.5	15.8	20.8	18.3	20.8
Disagree	6.7	7.5	6.7	5.0	5.0
strongly disagree	1.7	2.5	1.7	3.3	3.3
	100.0	100.0	100.0	100.0	.8
					99.2
					.8
					100.0

Figure 7

Table: 7.

The result table 7 showed that, 74.2% of the participants agreed that it is highly required to address the sociopolitical issues within the community. 8.4% of the respondents did not agree with the statement and 17.5% of the respondents neither agreed nor disagreed they remained neutral. From the second variable in table 7 it was revealed that 74.2% of the respondent believed in active participation in community. 10% of the participants did not agree and 15.8% of the respondents neither agreed nor disagreed they remained neutral. In the third variable from table 7, the result showed that, 80% of the respondents believed that taking part in community help in improving community. 8.4% of the respondents did not

agree with the statement and 20.8% neither agreed nor disagreed they remained neutral. From the fourth variable in table 7, the result revealed that, 73.3% of the respondent believed that active citizen work for the community. 8.3% of the participants did not agree and 18.3% of the respondents neither agreed nor disagreed they remained neutral. In the fifth variable from table 7, the result showed that, 69.2% of the participants believed that being an active citizen they will be responsible in arranging effective activities for providing solution to community problems. 8% of the respondents did not agree and 20.8% neither agreed nor disagreed they remained neutral

RESULT AND DISCUSSION

Civic Engagement and Social Responsibility

Civic engagement is an activity that is gateway to maintain democratic and social values. It also empowers the social ties among community members. Civic engagement is defined working to make a different life full of civic values and moral attitudes and a combination of knowledge that inculcate social responsibility and values and surely promote a good quality of life in a society. According to the literature found, all educational institutions around the globe should play their key role in highlighting the societal issues. (Issues contain poverty domestic local and governmental policies). Civic engagement through civic education bridges the gap and make a very responsible society.

Is one of the participants expressed?

“I believe it is our moral duty to learn civic values and teach our fellows, so we become responsible citizen of our country”

In past few years, the student’s environment in universities have changed rapidly. One of the core aspects found to be an online environment, culture of social media that has navigated the daily life of students. The face-to-face discussions, debates and circles have long been victimized due to individuality and busy routine. University students are in interaction through fast growing social media and social apps that has negatively reflected the social values. It is said that parental education is a key civic education. However, there is huge gap between the relationship of parent and their children. Therefore, in today’s world students don’t focus on learning social values and don’t ready to be engaged in civic values.

As one of respondents expressed that,

“We don’t know what the social responsibilities are. Nobody is ever taught and guided us about our values and laws. Therefore, we don’t care about breaking both government laws and society’s value. However, I believe we must engage ourselves to civic values and take social reasonability’s to make a positive society”.

CIVIC MANAGEMENT

Community engagement is ground with the aspect of social justice flowing, combination of knowledge skills, motivation, moral learning process including self-participation fulfill the needs and demands of the community. Civic engagement is a paradigm that, inculcate a social sense of responsibility among members of the society. It guides people to work for the wellbeing of the community and its members. Some of the activities of community members includes participations, group activities teamwork, and participation in building civil society, and benefiting the common good and community gardening. Similarly, civic engagement is an act that is foster to inculcate a sense of responsibility and make understand of one's social identity. The members of the community are empowered to become agent of social change worldwide and their become change agent for a more democratic value. To prove the statement one, the participant expressed that,

“It is our social responsibility to vote in every election. We are responsible to obey government laws and regulations that guides our life. We all member of the community should engage ourselves to know needs and demands of the community. Thus, we can create a positive society “

“It gives me an immense pleasure to engage myself in different activities for the well-being and development of the community. It is our first and foremost duty to help another within the same community so that we should know the problems of our community”.

Social and political responsibility is one the major key to civic engagement. Political sense of responsibility guides the community members about social and political issues that exist around. Through educational institutions the world is trying to make possible the culture of civic engagement. The culture of civic engagement helps communities both local and national level. It has been long duration the higher education is producing civically polished students who will serve their community as a leader who will be responsible in addressing both social and political issues of their communities. The task of promoting civic engagement is aware the graduates to aware socially and politically. To make them publicly involved requires a full understanding of the college learning environment for today's students. However, today's students (youths) are found to be less engaged in civic and political activities as they used to be in past. Students are found less interested in political activities. The reason found in the literature is that the adulthood has changed dramatically therefore voting and political responsibility also measured to be very less in numbers.

One of the respondents expressed

“It is our social and political responsibility to address our community issues in political platform. It will help community to solve both local and national issues”.

Role of Universities in managing Civic Values

Civic education is one of the most important aspects to prepare the students on rationally, make them responsible citizens and inculcate in them a true sense of citizenship. It is a true concept that deals with the core objectives, themes, and process through which a student learns and obtain skills. Civic education guides student about social, political, democratic, and religious values. It is a subject taught in many primary schools of the globe for the purpose to inculcate moral values among youths. The higher education (Collages/Universities) have been playing a vital role providing student with multiple opportunities to make them community oriented. The universities are working and focusing on civic education to prepare responsible citizen. They are producing goal-oriented students through service leaning courses, enhancing the critically thinking of students, creating a conducive environment for the youth through social groups, organizations to produce leaders and give them confidence of self-governance. The higher education’s social programs are increasing awareness about social and political issues, encouraging students to participate in community-based activities. Civic management has always link to educational institutions which a play a key role in inculcating social values among youths. The past research has shown that, there is a relationship between service participation and citizenship. According to (Hunter,2000) “conducted a cross-sectional study to examine the influence of service learning on students’ political attitudes and found that participation in service increased the likelihood of future participation, helped students learn more about their community, and developed students’ academic skills”.

As one of the respondents said that,

“I have learnt social service experiences from my teachers at university that has help me to work and take participation in community-based activities. My learning experiences helped me to improve the overall values and always tried to transfer those values to my friends and family. Through my university activities I am now able to take social responsibility and love to work for the development of my community”.

Similarly, the interviews revealed that, the most important predictor of civic management was the measurement and perception of the precipitants from the universities of Balochistan, it was explored that, the student who were interviewed found committed, to work for their community, who were found very positive with their opinions about community services.

They were willing to improve their community needs and demands and their behavior was observed to be equally important. Further, the result shows that, there is an important and positive impacts of civic education on student's level of commitment, resulting in community-based activities, cleaning up the environment, promoting social and political values, showing social responsibility, and helping others in difficulties. Furthermore, the results of the interviews and quantitative data reflected that both the students and institution share basic components between individuals and social agents (Agents of socialization) and their level of interconnectivity. A sense of responsibility is an essential agent of promoting civic values seem crucial for the development of their moral and social values. Therefore, students' involvement in promoting civic values is found very crucial.

As one of the interviewers expressed that,

“I have learnt many social ethics from my family and primary schools. My teachers have taught me how to respect my elders and community members. I am integrated to my community members, and I feel connected to community-based activities. I also learnt to promote both social and political values to my next generation. I am mutative and encouraged to be an active citizen”.

The concept of citizenship and civic sense in Balochistan is a very important concept not only attracts social scientists but also the new leaners and public. The wide range of perceptions and views revealed that, social attitude and its reflections is more actual in every life of citizens. Now a day in Balochistan the problem of noncompliance to civic values has increased in a drastic way and the situation is getting worsen with respect to government laws. The denial of national integrality and social diversity resulted in loss of decline and faith among youths in the province. There result portrayed a disharmony between the government and her interaction to citizen. The huge gap between the government (Local government) and the citizens have produced inferiority complex and resulted a civic identity crisis. The level of trust has decreased, bad governance, lack of accountability, corruption, law and order situation, political insatiability has disappointed the citizens. Therefore, the willingness to follow the government law and government services were not satisfactory by the many youths in the province. Therefore, one of the respondents expressed that,

“We felt that civic identity is, and integral part of community composed with our national and cultural identity. To follow and protect the self-identity and moral values of our community we need the support of our local government and politician. Thus, we can solve both our social and political problems”.

Active Citizen

It is one of the core responsibilities of every nation to produce good and active citizens through social institutions. It is true that, nations are sustained by citizens who have social-political knowledge, having sense of civic education, care for their own security, good quality of life and economic needs. To build a secure democracy and promote democratic culture civic education is emphasized both national and internal level. Literature is proved that education and civic education is the only factors that empower the nations. However, with respect to community development, knowledge, skills re required to protect the fundamental rights of citizens and motivate them to be an active member of their community. The indicators of a good citizens are the following

- To obey government law
- Cleaning environment
- Promoting moral and ethical knowledge
- Helping local and national government
- Participating in community-based activities
- Following religious and cultural elements
- Promoting democratic culture

Thus, the only target of civic education/values is to inculcate the above-mentioned points among the youths to make them active citizen. It is proved that the role of educational institutions is to produce responsible students, to enhance their critical thinking and produce future leaders. Therefore, the respondent gave high property to their university, reaching first time in their classes, accept to obey government laws, showed willingness to work for their community and clean environment.

As one the senior respondent explained that,

“I give high priority to my education/university. My institutions and instructors taught me to get myself engaged with community and work for the clean environment. Therefore, I always prefer reaching fist to my class. I always try to prefer my community and let others to do the same”

CONCLUSION

Overview of the Chapter

The final part of the research discusses the result and outcomes. This chapter is designed to deal with literature gap, Theoretical underpinning, and core concepts and more importantly to look at the future means of study. Besides this, it contains generalizability of the themes

and gives policy recommendation for the further research study. The section of the literature aims to deal with the core gaps and other problems. In the following chapter the core of summary is drawn to identify the main concepts. Main key concepts are identified to look at the factors promoting civic education and community development. The core concepts are put together to produce general theory of the phenomena that is currently being under discussion. Thus, the researcher assumed the main outcomes of the research for policy implication and will try to open the doors for the future research.

Identification of the Gap in the Literature

Civic education is positively influencing everyone in the countryside. The major problem identified in the review of the literature was the noncompliance to civic values and less participation of the youth in community-based activities like social participation, political participation but the emerging phenomenon and culture of civic values is connected to the social well-being of people. Therefore, it is becoming the core focus of researchers around the world. There were many studies related to civic education and civic management, but their major concern was role of higher education and social institutions. These studies helped the researcher to explore the core phenomena of civic management that was not studied much before. However, the past studies provide a useful framework for the researcher in future. Similarly, after keenly studying the literature some core literature gaps were pointed out. Conversely, some of the identified gaps are major in the context of universities in Balochistan. Undoubtedly, there were conducted many studies by scholars to identify the core concept of civic education. In the context of universities in Balochistan by investigating water the role and social well-being of people there was not any well-structured studies.

Considering, the core themes identified in the literature gaps, the social researchers has structured a study to explore the social impacts of civic education by taking universities of Balochistan the study area. In Balochistan UOB, SBK, UOUT were selected as a case study for the purpose to explore the associated issue and more importantly the social dilemma of civic management. Finally, the current study will remain to be uplift in the domain of higher education because the finding of the study has general phenomena for the policy makers to investigate the issue very seriously.

Summary and Discussion

Civic education and social wellbeing of citizens/students along with the core exploration

about the emerging phenomena have been the only themes of this research. The studied phenomena about civic education and management and community development in Balochistan are the main ground realities need more focus and by presenting the major themes of this thesis. It is needed to look at the social factors of civic education from the roots. Civic education is mostly associated with community, political stability, and accountability. However, the current result revealed that, there is a huge number of students who were showing interest in participating community-based activities and willing to work for the development of the community. No doubt government laws are key to community development but unfortunately, these rules are always violated by citizens. Student from the university accepted to obey the government laws. Therefore, civic education is very crucial for national development of nay nations. It is the backbone of societal development. It is always concerned with the fundamental rights of citizens, social responsibilities, and well as producing future leaders. Secondly, it is also the rules of higher education by maintaining social norms and values. Thus, preparation in civic life is an important factor to sustain our democratic form of government without sustaining civic life the concept of democracy will be lost. The bad governance is always associated with noncompliance to civic values. Therefore, it is our national responsibility to promote civic life among our youths to make them responsible and active citizens. Thus, the role of universities is very much crucial.

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